

Case Study

Marketing Efficiency of Orange in Gadingkulon Village, Dau District, Malang Regency, Indonesia

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Abstract

Efficient marketing will prosper the actors in each marketing agency, producers and consumers. Efficiency will be created if marketing costs can be minimized so that the percentage of producer prices to consumers is not too large, and there is no gap in the profit ratio to marketing costs between marketing agencies. The study aims to analyze marketing efficiency of tangerines and siamese in Gadingkulon Village. Data were collected from 87 citrus farmers who were selected by simple random sampling. Traders were determined by snowball sampling, consist of 17 collectors, 5 wholesalers, and 7 retailers were selected. Data were edited in the field, tabulated, compiled, then presented in tabular form, analyzed and described. The results showed that tangerines and siamese in Gadingkulon Village had an imperfect competitive market structure which was monopolistic. Marketing of the two types of oranges involves four channels i.e. collectors, retailers (inside and outside Malang Regency), and wholesalers. Oranges marketing system is not yet efficient, where wholesalers have larger profit margin ratio than other market players. Marketing channels I and II for tangerines are more efficient than channels III and IV. Meanwhile, marketing channel I for siamese is more efficient than channel II, III, and IV.

Keywords: Margin, marketing, efficiency, tangerine, siamese.

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Introduction

Marketing plays an important role to stimulate production and consumption and accelerates the pace of economic development of a country. Horticultural marketing in India is highly decentralized. It is very complex because of perishable nature, seasonality and bulkiness, i.e. oranges (Mahanta & Konwar, 2014). Oranges are also one of the commodities that have market opportunities in Bangladesh (Begum et al., 2016). As an important commodity in Indonesia, most orange producers currently sell their crops without grading. Parasharam & Neeraj (2017) revealed that maximum losses occurred at the farmer, which were mainly due to improper handling of produce after harvesting. However, siamese farming in West Sumatera has a high comparative advantage (Romdhon et al., 2018).

In Indonesia, the slightly rate of farmers' adoption of innovative technologies is caused by the sluggish process of dissemination, and transfer of recommended technology, and the fragility of the farmer institutions themselves. As a result, production process becomes poor and uncoordinated, so the fruit produced is varied and of low quality. Lack of coordination in the process of production, harvesting and marketing in agribusiness areas consisting of many small farmers causes low competitiveness. As a result, bargaining position of farmers will continue to weaken, especially in marketing. The situation also occurs in the marketing of mandarin oranges in Nepal (Shrestha, 2015). Merchants have a dominant role in both purchasing of mandarin from producers and supplying to other districts. Majority of producers were not getting adequate training, support and supervision from concerned organizations. Major weakness in mandarin value chain was unorganized marketing system. However, Zenginoglu & Dijk (2006) revealed that Turkey's oranges exports to the EU are determined by quality demanded by consumers, the availability of the fruits, and the presence of competing countries. Rachmi et al. (2018) also stated that Indonesia needs to improve marketing efficiency of local oranges in order to compete with imported oranges because the two products were substitutes. The decline in the price of imported oranges from China will reduce the market share of local oranges. Pudjiastuti (2014); Pudjiastuti et al. (2013); Pudjiastuti & Kembauw (2018) also found that it would disrupt the trade balance in Indonesia.

Post-harvest handling of oranges by farmers has not been carried out properly. The fruit is often harvested by traders who harvest fruit of all sizes with varying degrees of fruit maturity without using pruning shears, i.e. twisting and pulling the fruit by hand. The condition is made worse if the sale of fruit by farmers is carried out using an "ijon" system (ijon = traders buy oranges to farmers before harvest and there is an agreement on the price at that time), where the time for picking them are determined by the middleman. Oranges harvested can be overdue so that the quality is poor and can reduce tree's health and affect fruit harvests in the following year (Supriyanto & Zamzami, 2014). It is no different in Vietnam, where the farms' owners have extensive experience in orange cultivation and receive periodic technical training, they still have low levels of education and a lack of economic management expertise (Nguyen et al., 2020). In India, the most common and important constraint in marketing of fruits was cartelisation among traders. The imperfect market structure forces the farmers to enter into a forward contract that sets a minimum price, rather at the dissatisfaction of the farmer, as an insurance against possible lower price at later stages (Bhat et al., 2015; Chand et al., 2021; Deka et al.,

2020). Oranges marketing performance like this, also happened in Nigeria (Girei et al., 2020).

Unfortunately, in these unfavorable conditions, even oranges farmers can't do anything. Fruit grading is usually done by collectors before being packaged for shipping, or by other traders when selling them. Bargaining position of farmers is no vigorous due to the fragility of farmer institutions, resulting in oranges marketing not being in favor of farmers. Fragility of the institutions means that harvesting and marketing cannot be coordinated as a group. As a result, farmers have to deal directly with middlemen and/or collecting traders with a lot of capital, who, apart from understanding the ins and outs of marketing oranges, are even aware of the daily needs of farmers' households. Oranges marketing system in Indonesia was considered inefficient. Existing research shows that marketing costs in Indonesia are high and the distribution of remuneration is still asymmetrically among large traders, while farmers and collectors receive a slight share. Research by Husnarti & Ranti (2018) regarding the marketing efficiency of oranges in production centers in Jember, East Java, shows that market structure and market performance are considered inefficient because the price share received by farmers is relatively small. Marketing channel that has the smallest marketing margin and the largest farmer share is the most efficient marketing channel, or the farmer share is greater than the marketing margin (Anita et al., 2012).

Dau District, which is located in Malang Regency, is a center for oranges production. In 2020, the region produced 3,499.73 tonnes of oranges, significantly higher than avocados (39.48 tonnes) and papayas (17 tonnes) (BPS, 2021). During the COVID-19 pandemic, the demand for oranges increased because the fruit contains a lot of vitamin C. There is a lot of market demand for a commodity (particularly tangerine or orange), while production (supply) is relatively constant, will cause the commodity price concerned to increase. Who will benefit from the increasing price is an interesting subject to analyze. Furthermore, given that during the pandemic covid-19 there is a mobility restriction policy, how about the marketing performance? The purpose of this study was to analyze marketing efficiency of tangerines and siamese in Gadingkulon Village, the center of oranges production in Dau District.

Research Methods

The research was conducted in Gadingkulon Village, Dau District, because it is a center of oranges plantations in Malang Regency. The main commodities cultivated by farmers were tangerines and siamese.

Respondent were distinguished into three category, that are tangerine farmers, siamese farmers and traders. The population of farmers were all farmers who cultivate both types of oranges and the quantity were 343 farmers. The number of oranges farmers as respondents was determined as many as 87 farmers. Each farmer was selected by simple random sampling. Merchant respondents were determined using snowball sampling, 17 collectors, 5 wholesalers, and 7 retailers were selected.

Data collected in the field, edited first and cross-checked again to the farmers to avoid the mistakes. Marketing efficiency of tangerines and siamese was analyzed using

structure, conduct, and performance (SCP) approach. The analysis step begins by identifying the marketing channels of oranges with the prices received and costs incurred in each marketing agency, as well as describing them.

Market structure of oranges was identified based on the number of farmers, buyers (traders), barriers to entry and exit to the oranges market in Gadingkulon Village, and product differentiation. Market behavior (conduct) was identified through pricing methods, sales promotion, price or non-price competition among farmers and traders. Market performance was analyzed using farmer's share parameters and marketing margin. The parameter is also used to measure marketing efficiency of oranges.

a. *Farmer's Share*

Farmer's share analysis aims to determine the share of prices received by farmers (producers). If the parameter is greater, then the market performance will be better in the producer side. Farmers's share is formulated as (Anindita & Baladina, 2017):

$$\text{Farmer's Share} = \frac{P_f}{P_r} \times 100\% \quad (1)$$

P_f = Farmers' price

P_r = Retailers' price

b. *Marketing Margin*

Marketing margin is the difference between the consumers' price and the farmers' price. Components of this parameter consist of the costs incurred by each marketing agency in carrying out marketing functions and the profits to be obtained by the marketing agency. Therefore, size of the marketing margin is basically sum of the costs and profits received by the marketing agency. Marketing margin is calculated by the formula:

$$M_p = P_r - P_f \quad (2)$$

M_p = Marketing Margin

Distribution of marketing margins in each institution can be calculated using Profit Margin Ratio (RPM) as:

$$\text{RPM} = \frac{\text{Marketing Profit}}{\text{Marketing Cost}} \quad (3)$$

Marketing profit = sales value – marketing cost

Marketing cost = labor cost + distribution cost + depreciation

Marketing efficiency occurs if the marketing agency is able to deliver goods from producers to consumers at minimum costs and realize a fair distribution of the total price paid by final consumers to all parties participating in the production and marketing activities of these goods.

Results and Discussions

Marketing of Tangerines and Siamese in Gadingkulon Village

Marketing of Tangerines and Siamese Oranges in Gadingkulon Village

Gadingkulon Village is administratively located in the Dau District, Malang Regency. Geographically, it is located on the northern hillside of Mount Kawi and the southern part of Mount Panderman, so the weather is cool, the scenery is beautiful, and the soil is fertile. These various aspects make it has potential in oranges farming and ecotourism. The topography is mainland and mostly hills with an altitude of 670 meters above sea level with temperature of 20° C - 27°C and rainfall reaches 2,400 mm/year. Gading Kulon Village consists of three hamlets i.e. Krajan, Sempu and Princi. Tangerines and siamese are widely cultivated by farmers because of the suitability with the local climate. In this area, an oranges picking tourist area has also been established to attract visitors to improve the economy of the village community, especially oranges farmers.

Marketing of tangerines and siamese in Gadingkulon Village involves several marketing institutions including collectors, wholesalers and retailers (Figure 1). It also exists in the marketing of oranges domestically (Dewanti et al., 2015; Husnarti & Ranti, 2018; Romdhon et al., 2018) as well as abroad such as in Nigeria (Fakayode et al., 2010), India (Mahanta & Konwar, 2014), and Vietnam (Nguyen et al., 2020). Figure 1 shows that the process of transferring tangerines and siamese oranges from farmers in Gadingkulon Village to consumers is carried out through four marketing channels. These marketing channels were generally realized because of the relationships that have been built by farmers with traders. The four marketing channels were: I. Farmers – retailers – consumers; II. Farmers – collectors – retailers – consumers; III. Farmers – wholesalers – retailers – consumers; IV. Farmers – collectors – wholesalers – retailers – consumers.

Figure 1. Marketing Channels of Tangerines and Siamese in Gadingkulon Village

- Marketing Channels I
- Marketing Channels II
- Marketing Channels III
- Marketing Channels IV

Collecting traders in the village are generally oranges farmers who are 26-62 years old, have 8-32 years of oranges farming experience and 2-20 years of trading experience, elementary-high school education and 3-5 family members. All oranges farmers in Gadingkulon Village sell their product to collectors. The trust given by farmers to collecting traders arises because of the close relationship that has been established as fellow farmers. Farmers will also borrow amount of money from them when they need it, both for productive and consumptive purposes. These traders also understand the quality of oranges produced by farmers, because they also know how to cultivate and technology used. Each collector has partnerships with 10-35 farmers.

On the other hand, some farmers also sell oranges directly to wholesalers and retailers. Generally, the farmers are those who also act as traders. Wholesalers buy oranges from two sources, i.e. farmers and collectors. Wholesalers buy oranges from farmers at a lower price than buying from collectors. Retailers buy oranges from three sources, namely farmers, collectors and wholesalers. Purchase prices and selling prices in each marketing agency and marketing channel can be seen in Table 1.

Table 1. Price of Tangerines and Siamese in Each Marketing Agency, 2021

Marketing Agency	Tangerines		Siamese	
	Purchase price	Selling price	Purchase price	Selling price
----- IDR/kg -----				
I. Farmer – retailer – consumer				
1. Farmer	-	8103	-	10000
2. Retailer	8103	15000	10000	17000
3. Consumer	15000	-	17000	-
II. Farmer – collector – retailer – consumer				
1. Farmer	-	8103	-	10000
2. Collector	8103	10000	10000	12000
3. Retailer	10000	15000	12000	17000
4. Consumer	15000	-	17000	-
III. Farmer – wholeseller – retailer – consumer				
1. Farmer	-	8103	-	10000
2. Wholeseller	8103	15000	10000	17000
3. Retailer	15000	20000	17000	22000
4. Consumer	20000	-	22000	-
IV. Farmer – collector – wholeseller – retailer – consumer				
1. Farmer	-	8103	-	10000
2. Collector	8103	10000	10000	12000
3. Wholeseller	10000	15000	12000	17000
4. Retailer	15000	17000	20000	22000
5. Consumer	20000	-	22000	-

Marketing Efficiency of Tangerines and Siamese

Conceptually, marketing efficiency can be identified through market structure, market behavior and market performance. Market structure will determine how market participants behave, which in turn will determine the market performance. Furthermore, it will explain the market structure, market behavior and market performance of tangerines and siamese in Gadingkulon Village which were used to analyze their marketing efficiency.

Market Structure

Market structure can be identified from the number of sellers and buyers, product homogeneity, barriers to entry and exit from the market, and information about the market. Tangerines and siamese in Gadingkulon Village were produced by 343 farmers. Two types of oranges are only distinguished by their size. The farmers sell oranges to 17 traders in Gadingkulon Village and have established partnerships for more than 10 years. Farmers can also sell oranges to retailers or wholesalers. It can be said that the orange market structure in this region is classified as monopolistic.

The market structure (monopolistic) is more efficient than other market structures (oligopoly and monopoly). Competition in this market tends to be less intense because there are 17 traders in the village. Orange market in this village is dominated by the fruit produced in this area as well. Barriers to market entry for traders from outside were created because of the partnership between oranges farmers and village collectors. It is possible for wholesalers and retailers to enter this market if they have kinship relations with farmers and village collectors. However, existing new merchants at the moment also shows that the barriers to entering the oranges market in this village are not too tight.

Market Conduct

Market behavior is approached by marketing channels, selling and buying practices, pricing systems, and payment systems. Information about the oranges price and demand, both from within and outside the city, can be obtained at the sales office located in Dusun Sempu RW 02 RT 05. Existence of this office is very helpful for village collectors in distributing oranges to various destination city. Tangerines and siamese generally have equally quality as other oranges cultivated in Dau District. The primary distinction is only in the size. During the COVID-19 pandemic, the demand for oranges in this village relatively fixed in large numbers, but with different quantities depending on the destination city.

Traders from outside the region usually order directly through the sales office. However, bargaining power of oranges farmers in determining prices remains poor. Oranges price is generally determined by village collectors. A classic event that always occurs in the trade of agricultural commodities, because of its perishable nature.

Farmers usually sell oranges without grading, sorting and promoting. Oranges were sold on a wholesale basis, where they buy directly from farmers who harvest in the garden, and the cost of harvesting is charged to them. Payment of this transaction is agreed in cash. The selling price at the farmer is IDR 8,103 per kg for tangerines and IDR 10,000

per kg for siamese. The difference in selling prices in each marketing channel varies (see Table 1) due to damaged oranges (depreciation), labor costs, distribution costs and the profits earned by each marketing agency.

Market Performance

Marketing performance in this study was measured by marketing margin and several related parameters to analyze the marketing efficiency of tangerines and siamese. The various parameters for each marketing channel are presented in Table 2 and Table 3.

Table 2. Marketing Margin Tangerines in Gadingkulon Village, 2021

Description	Channel I	Channel II	Channel III	Channel IV
Farmer				
Farming Cost (IDR/kg)	3.036	3.036	3.036	3.036
Selling Price (IDR/Kg)	8.103	8.103	8.103	8.103
Farmer Share (%)	54	54	40,5	40,5
Profit (IDR/kg)	5.067	5.067	5.067	5.067
Ratio Profit Margin (RPM)	1,67	1,67	1,67	1,67
Collector				
Selling Price (IDR/Kg)		10.000		10.000
Labor Cost (IDR/Kg)		516,5		516,5
Distribution Cost (IDR/Kg)		241		240,9
Depreciation (IDR/Kg)		174,5		174,5
Marketing Margin (IDR/Kg)		1.897		1.897
Profit Marjin (IDR/Kg)		965		965
RPM		1,04		1,04
Retailer (inside)				
Selling Price (IDR/Kg)	15.000	15.000		
Labor Cost (IDR/Kg)	600	600		
Distribution Cost (Rp/Kg)	1.000	1.000		
Depreciation (IDR/Kg)	1.537	1.537		
Marketing Margin (IDR/Kg)	6.897	5.000		
Profit Marjin (IDR/Kg)	3.760	1.863		
RPM	1,20	0,59		
Wholeseller				
Selling price (IDR/Kg)			15.000	15.000
Labor Cost (IDR/Kg)			304,4	304,4
Distribution Cost (Rp/Kg)			452,2	452,2
Depreciation (IDR/Kg)			503,8	621,7
Marketing Margin (IDR/Kg)			6.897	5.000
Profit Marjin (IDR/Kg)			5.636,6	3.621,7
RPM			4,47	2,63
Retailer (outside)				
Selling Price (IDR/Kg)			20.000	20.000
Depreciation (IDR/Kg)			2.306	2.306
Marketing Margin (IDR/Kg)			5.000	5.000

Description	Channel I	Channel II	Channel III	Channel IV
Profit Marjin (IDR/Kg)			2.694	2.694
RPM			1,17	1,17
Consumer				
Purchase Price (IDR/Kg)	15.000	15.000	20.000	20.000

Collectors, retailers (inside the city) and wholesalers incur labor costs, distribution costs and depreciation costs. The latter costs arise because of the characteristics of oranges as an agricultural commodity which is generally perishable. During storage, the percentage of damaged oranges varies depending on the packaging and the mode of transportation used. Collectors and retailers in the city use pick-ups, while wholesalers use trucks. Retailers (outside the city) do not incur labor costs and distribution costs, because oranges are delivered on the spot. Each retailer buys 250-350 kg, while each wholesaler buys 23-28 tons of oranges.

Table 3. Marketing Margin Siamese in Gadingkulon Village, 2021

Description	Channel I	Channel II	Channel III	Channel IV
Farmer				
Farming Cost (IDR/kg)	3.384	3.384	3.384	3.384
Selling Price (IDR/Kg)	10.000	10.000	10.000	10.000
Farmer Share (%)	58,8	58,8	45,5	45,5
Profit (IDR/kg)	6.616	6.616	6.616	6.616
Ratio Profit Margin (RPM)	1,96	1,96	1,96	1,96
Collector				
Selling Price (IDR/Kg)		12.000		12.000
Labor Cost (IDR/Kg)		447,8		447,8
Distribution Cost (IDR/Kg)		208,9		208,9
Depreciation (IDR/Kg)		416,5		416,5
Marketing Margin (IDR/Kg)		2.000		2.000
Profit Marjin (IDR/Kg)		926,8		926,8
RPM		0,86		0,86
Retailer (inside)				
Selling Price (IDR/Kg)	17.000	17.000		
Labor Cost (IDR/Kg)	429	429		
Distribution Cost (Rp/Kg)	714	714		
Depreciation (IDR/Kg)	1.842	1.842		
Marketing Margin (IDR/Kg)	7.000	5.000		
Profit Marjin (IDR/Kg)	4.015	2.015		
RPM	1,35	0,67		
Wholeseller				
Selling price (IDR/Kg)			17.000	17.000
Labor Cost (IDR/Kg)			250	250
Distribution Cost (Rp/Kg)			371,5	371,5
Depreciation (IDR/Kg)			621,4	745,7
Marketing Margin (IDR/Kg)			7.000	5.000

Description	Channel I	Channel II	Channel III	Channel IV
Profit Marjin (IDR/Kg)			5.757,1	3.757,1
RPM			4,63	3,02
Retailer (outside)				
Selling Price (IDR/Kg)			22.000	22.000
Depreciation (IDR/Kg)			2.609	2.609
Marketing Margin (IDR/Kg)			5.000	5.000
Profit Marjin (IDR/Kg)			2.391	2.391
RPM			0,92	0,92
Consumer				
Purchase Price (IDR/Kg)	17.000	17.000	22.000	22.000

Farmer gate price of tangerines did not differ for all marketing channels, but the selling price at retailers was higher with the length of the marketing channel (Table 2). Farmer share in marketing channels I and II, which is higher than marketing channels III and IV. It revealed that the involvement of wholesalers in the marketing of oranges led to a decrease in farmer share. Because farmers receive the same price of tangerines, both from village collectors, retailers and wholesalers, there is no difference in farmers' profits in each marketing channel. However, $RPM > 1$ indicates that farmer's profit is higher than the cost.

In marketing channels I and II, retailers (inside the city) will receive higher profits if they buy oranges directly from farmers rather than buying from collectors. Retailers can buy tangerines at a lower price if they have a partnership with farmers. Sometimes, farmers who have retailer partners are those who also act as collectors. However, retailers can only buy tangerines directly from farmers during the harvest season. Retailers who buy oranges through collectors have $RPM < 1$, meaning that their profits are smaller than costs. It is different from other marketing agencies in each existing marketing channel, where the RPM is > 1 . Wholesalers have the highest RPMs. This fact is an indication that the marketing of tangerines in Gadingkulon Village has not been efficient. Marketing channels I and II are more efficient than marketing channels III and IV.

As in the marketing of tangerines, there is no difference in the selling price of siamese at farmers for all marketing channels, but the selling price at retailers is higher with the length of the marketing channel (Table 3). Farmer share in marketing channels I and II is higher than in marketing channels III and IV. It also reveals that the involvement of wholesalers causes a decrease in farmer share. Because the price of oranges is equal in each marketing channel, the profits received by farmers were also not different. $RPM > 1$ indicates that the farmer's profit is higher than the cost.

In marketing channels I and II, it can be seen that retailers in the city will receive higher profits if they buy directly from orange farmers compared to buying from village collectors. Retailers can buy Siamese oranges at a lower price if they have a partnership with farmers. Retailers who buy oranges through collectors have their $RPM < 1$, meaning that their profits are smaller than their costs. In contrast to the marketing of tangerines, village collectors, and retailers outside the city, the RPM is < 1 . Wholesalers have the largest RPM. This finding is an indication that the marketing of siamese in Gadingkulon

Village is also not efficient. Marketing channel I is more efficient than marketing channel II, III and IV.

Conclusions

Tangerines and siamese in Gadingkulon Village have a monopolistic market structure. The marketing of the two types of oranges involves four channels with village collectors, retailers (inside), wholesalers and retailers (outside). Farmers sell oranges that are ready to be harvested to traders in bulk, where the cost of harvesting is imposed by the traders. Prices were determined by the merchants and were paid in cash. Marketing system for tangerines and siamese is not efficient, where wholesalers have a much larger RPM than other market players. Marketing channels I and II for tangerines are more efficient than marketing channels III and IV. Meanwhile, marketing channel I for siamese is more efficient than marketing channel II, III, and IV.

The limitation of this study is that it does not differentiate between tangerines and siamese according to their size. Grading is carried out by the marketing agency closest to the consumer in order to cover losses due to damaged oranges during the sales process. The abundance of oranges in this area and the dependence of farmers on wholesalers who have the ability to buy in large quantities, as well as the characteristics of oranges that are easily damaged, open up opportunities for the establishment of a tangerine and siamese processing business.

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